

Preparation and Kinetics of Aquation of *cis*- β -chloropyridine (trien) cobalt(III) and *cis*- β -chloroaniline (trien) cobalt(III) Cations.

ANADI C. DASH, NAYAN K. MOHANTY and RABINDRA K. NANDA

Department of Chemistry, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar-4

The preparation and kinetics of aquation of the title cations are reported. The rate studies indicate that these complexes have been isolated in one topological form. Attempt to prepare the corresponding α isomer from pure *cis*- α -[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl and the amine was not successful. In the range of hydrogen ion concentration, 0.005-0.2M, the rate law of aquation takes the form, $-\text{dln}[\text{Co}(\text{III})]/\text{dt} = k_1 + k_2 [\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ where k_1 and k_2 are the rate constants for the spontaneous and inverse acid dependent paths respectively. The latter path is believed to involve the conjugate base as the reactive species. Deprotonation of the secondary NH₂ group of the coordinated trien is the most likely source of the conjugate base of [Co(trien)(Py)Cl]²⁺. The nature of the conjugate base of the aniline complex is, however, less certain as it may arise due to the deprotonation of the secondary NH₂ group of trien as well as the NH-proton of the coordinated aniline. Mechanism of aquation of the trien complex is essentially dissociative.

BASOLO *et al.*¹ investigated the rate of aquation of *cis* [Co(trien)(NH₃)Cl]²⁺ and reported that this complex aquates about 2 times slower than *cis* [Co(en)₂(NH₃)Cl]²⁺ under comparable conditions. Subsequently several publications on the synthesis and stereochemistry of disubstituted cobalt(III) triethylenetetramine complexes have appeared²⁻⁷. Disregarding the conformational isomerism of the trien skeleton, the disubstituted cobalt(III) trien cation, [Co(trien)X₂]⁺ (X = Cl or Br) can exist in three topological forms such as *trans*-, *cis*- α and *cis*- β (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

Each of the forms when allowed to react with an amine ligand may yield the monohalogeno complex, [Co(trien)(amine)X]²⁺ under suitable experimental conditions. It can be easily visualised that only the *cis*- β -[Co(trien)X₂]⁺ may yield two isomers on replacement of X by the amine ligand i.e. one due to the replacement of X *trans*-to NH₂ and another due to the replacement of X *cis*-to NH₂. The stereochemistry of all these isomers of the monohalogenoamine (trien) cobalt(III) complexes will be, however, still more complicated due to the conformational isomerism of the trien ligand as dictated by the NH₂ groups. Thus the trien complexes provide models for the study of the influence of stereochemistry of the nonlabile amine ligand on the rates and mechanisms of ligand substitution at the cobalt(III) centre. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to

synthesise suitable complexes of the type [Co(trien)(amine)X]²⁺ (X = Cl or Br) and study their kinetics of substitution. The present work deals with the synthesis and kinetics of aquation of one of the β isomers of *cis*-[Co(trien)(aniline)Cl]²⁺ and *cis*-[Co(trien)(pyridine)Cl]²⁺ cations.

Experimental

The crude *cis*- α -dichloro (trien) cobalt(III) chloride was prepared by aeration⁸ of a mixture of triethylenetetramine (Riedel) and cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (B.D.H.) followed by acidification of the mixture with conc. HCl and evaporation of the resulting solution to a small bulk till the complex crystallized out. The crude sample was washed with ethanol, diethyl ether and dried at 120° for several hours. It was recrystallized from hot 5M HCl. The *cis*- β dichloro (trien) cobalt(III) chloride was prepared by the method of Sargeson and Searle⁵.

Preparation of *cis*-chloroamine (trien) cobalt(III) perchlorate.

6g. of crude *cis*- α -dichloro (trien) cobalt(III) chloride was slurried with water in a mortar and triturated with 10% excess of amine until no further colour change was observed. The crude product was washed with ethanol and diethyl ether. The chloride salt was directly converted to perchlorate by crystallization from perchloric acid solution at 0°C. After two such crystallizations the product was found to be free from any outer-sphere chloride. The pure perchlorate salt so obtained was successively washed with ice cold water, ethanol and diethyl ether and stored over fused calcium chloride. The sample analyses as: Found: Co, 11.14; Cl, 6.48. Calc. for [Co(trien)(aniline)Cl](ClO₄)₂: Co, 11.07; Cl, 6.67. Found: Co, 11.20; Cl, 6.78. Calc. for [Co(trien)(pyridine)Cl](ClO₄)₂: Co, 11.30; Cl, 6.85%.

The compound obtained from *cis*-β-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl and pyridine by the procedure mentioned above was converted to the perchlorate form. The perchlorate salt was analysed for the bound chloride. {Found : Cl, 6.72. Calc. for [Co(trien) (pyridine)Cl] (ClO₄)₂ : Cl, 6.85%}. Pure *cis*-α-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl was allowed to react with pyridine for several hours at room temperature. There was no visual colour change. After 24 hours the mixture was washed with ethanol and diethyl ether and then recrystallized from HClO₄ solution at 0° till free from ionic chloride. The product after desiccation was analysed for bound chloride. Found : Cl, 12.0. Calc. for [Co(trien)Cl₂]ClO₄ : Cl, 18.9% ; Calc. for [Co(trien)Cl (OH₂)₁] (ClO₄)₂ : Cl, 7.76%}. Evidently the interaction of pyridine with pure *cis*-α-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl does not yield the desired chloropyridine product.

The spectra were recorded in a Beckman DK 2 spectrophotometer. The visible spectral data for the chloro amine complexes from crude *cis*-α-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl and *cis*-β-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl are very much similar (Table 1).

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA FOR [Co(trien)(amine)Cl](ClO₄)₂ IN 0.01 M HClO₄.

Amine	λ _{max} , mμ	ε _{max} , M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹		
pyridine	476 ^a	477 ^b	118 ^a	121 ^b
	and 370 ^a	370 ^b	107	113
aniline	522 ^a		124 ^a	

^a product from crude *cis*-α-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl
^b product from *cis*-β-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl

a weighed amount of complex was transferred to the reaction flask. The complex dissolved rapidly on shaking and the volume was made up with distilled water previously equilibrated at the reaction temperature. 5 ml of the reaction mixture was withdrawn at definite time intervals and the liberated chloride was estimated potentiometrically using 0.01 M AgNO₃. The pseudo-first-order rate constants were obtained from the gradients of the plots of log (V_∞ - V_t) against time. Runs were taken at least in duplicate.

Results

The rate data are collected in Tables 2 and 3. It is interesting to note that the chloropyridine complex derived from *cis*-β-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl and crude *cis*-α-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl reacts virtually at the same rate under identical experimental conditions. This is taken as evidence for the identical nature of the [Co(trien)(pyridine)Cl]²⁺ prepared by either of the two methods. Since pure *cis*-α-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl did not yield the desired product with pyridine it appears reasonable that axial ligation of amine is preferred. We believe that the complexes [Co(trien)(amine)Cl]²⁺, have the structure with the entering amine ligand *trans*- to the NH₂- group of trien (Fig. 1, C).

k_{obs} is found to increase with decreasing [H⁺]. The rate data fit best to the rate law in equation (1) ;

$$-d\ln[\text{Co(III)}]/dt = k_{obs} = k_1 + k_2 [\text{H}^+]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where k₁ and k₂ stand for the aquation rate constants for the acid independent and acid dependent paths respectively. The inverse acid dependence of k_{obs} is ascribed to the operation of base hydrolysis reaction.

TABLE 2—RATE DATA FOR THE AQUATION OF *cis*-β-[Co(trien)(pyridine)Cl]²⁺ WITH [complex]_T = 5.0 × 10⁻³ - 7.5 × 10⁻³ M ; I = 0.3 M.

[HClO ₄], M	45.0°		50.5°	55.5°
	10 ⁴ k _{obs} , sec ⁻¹			
0.005	1.36 ± 0.04	1.41 ± 0.03		
0.006	1.32 ± 0.02	1.20 ± 0.01 ^a		
0.0075	0.98 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.01 ^a	1.81 ± 0.03	2.52 ± 0.10
0.010	0.72 ± 0.02			
0.015	0.54 ± 0.01		0.94 ± 0.02	
0.020				1.44 ± 0.01
0.05	0.18 ± 0.01		0.32 ± 0.03	0.71 ± 0.01
0.10	0.10 ± 0.01		0.20 ± 0.02	0.43 ± 0.01
0.20			0.17 ± 0.01	
10 ³ k ₁ , sec ⁻¹	0.39 ± 0.17		0.80 ± 0.10	1.95 ± 0.20
10 ⁶ k ₂ , M sec ⁻¹	0.70 ± 0.01		1.30 ± 0.03	2.49 ± 0.06

^a complex derived from *cis*-β-[Co(trien)Cl₂]Cl.

Kinetics : The rates of aquation were studied in perchlorate medium at 45, 50 and 55°C. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) and perchloric acid (E. Merck) were used to adjust ionic strength and acidity of the reaction medium respectively. Solutions of desired composition were prepared in 50 ml measuring flasks and thermostatted. After thermal equilibrium was reached

[OH⁻] being < 10⁻¹¹ conjugate base (C. B.) mechanism involving acid ionisation of the secondary NH- group of trien and NH₂- group of coordinated aniline is preferred to the direct SN₂ reaction of OH⁻ with the chloro complexes in the acid dependent path. The exact nature of the reactive conjugate base of the aniline complex is, however, not certain.

Rate data when analysed by equation (1) yielded the values of k_1 and k_2 , which are also presented in Tables 2 and 3.

TABLE 3—RATE DATA FOR THE AQUATION OF *cis*- β -[Co(trien)(aniline)Cl]²⁺ WITH [complex]_T=0.003 M AND I=0.1 M.

[HClO ₄], M	45.0	50.5	55.5°C
	10 ⁶ k _{obs} , sec ⁻¹		
0.02		8.18 ± 0.13	20.1 ± 0.8
0.01	3.87 ± 0.15	8.64 ± 0.10	22.8 ± 0.2
0.0075	5.05 ± 0.10	9.69 ± 0.20	25.6 ± 0.1
0.005	8.25 ± 0.20	12.6 ± 0.20	33.0 ± 0.4
10 ⁶ k ₁ , sec ⁻¹	2.5 ± 0.1	6.0 ± 0.1	15.0 ± 0.1
10 ⁶ k ₂ , sec ⁻¹ M	2.7 ± 0.2	3.1 ± 0.2	8.5 ± 0.1

TABLE 4.—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE RATE OF AQUATION OF *cis*- β -[Co(trien)(pyridine)Cl]²⁺.

I, M	[H ⁺] _T =0.015 M, 50.5°C			
	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.05
10 ⁶ k _{obs} , sec ⁻¹	0.94 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.03	1.24 ± 0.01	1.46 ± 0.01

k_{obs} values for the pyridine complex at I=0.05–0.3M, [H⁺]=0.015 and 50°C are presented in table 4. k_{obs} decreases with ionic strength. The rate parameters k_1 and k_2 ($k_2=k_2' K_{NH}$) will be insensitive to ionic strength as one of the reactants is uncharged. Perchlorate ion is not expected to influence the rate of aquation of [Co (trien) (pyridine) Cl]²⁺. But K_{NH} is expected to decrease with ionic strength. As such the rate retardation of ionic strength is in keeping with the proposed conjugate base mechanism.

Discussion

Rate and activation parameters for the aquation reaction of *cis*- β -[Co (trien) (amine) Cl]²⁺ and *cis*-[Co (en)₂ (amine) Cl]²⁺ (amine=aniline¹⁰ or pyridine^{11,12}) are collected in Table 5.

The difference between spontaneous aquation rate constants (k_1) of trien and bis ethylenediamine complexes for the same amine ligand is rather small. The activation parameters for this path of both the trien complexes are comparable. The activation enthalpies and entropies of the corresponding bis ethylenediamine

TABLE 5—RATE AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF THE ACID INDEPENDENT AQUATION OF *cis*-[CoL(amine)Cl]²⁺.

L	amine	10 ⁶ k ₁ (50°), sec ⁻¹	ΔH‡, k. cal. mol ⁻¹	ΔS‡, cal. deg. ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
2 en	aniline	0.70 ^a	26.4	8
	pyridine	1.46 ± 0.04 ^b , 1.1 ^c	23.8 ^b	-5 ^b
trien	aniline	0.6	35.7 ± 3.0	26
	pyridine	0.8	34.6 ± 3.5	25

^a I=0.07 M (ClO₄⁻), ref. (10).

^b I=0.1 M (NO₃⁻), ref. (11).

^c I=0.01 M (ClO₄⁻), ref. (12).

complexes are somewhat lower than the same for the trien complexes. This might be either due to the difference in mechanism for the both series of complexes or due to relatively weaker solvation of the trien complexes in the transition state compared to the corresponding bis ethylenediamine complexes. Moreover it has been argued from the consideration of the activation entropies that the spontaneous aquation of *cis*-[Co (en)₂ (amine) Cl]²⁺ irrespective of the nature of the amine involves a dissociative transition state which is grossly tetragonal¹³. Whether such a transition state involved in the spontaneous aquation path of the trien complexes, under study, is yet to be established.

The values of k_2 at 50°C for chloro pyridine and chloro aniline complexes of the trien ligand are 1.3 × 10⁻⁶ (I=0.3M) and 3.1 × 10⁻⁸ M sec⁻¹ (I=0.1M) respectively. The difference in the values of k_2 is large and can not be accounted for by the ionic strength effect. Perhaps the observed reactivity difference in the k_2 path points to the fact that the nature of the conjugate bases of these complexes is strongly dependent on the amine ligand i.e. pyridine or aniline. In this context it is worth mentioning that the rate of base hydrolysis of *cis*-[Co (en)₂ (pyridine) Cl]²⁺ has been reported to be abnormally high¹². The rate constant k_2 for [Co (trien) (aniline) Cl]²⁺ compares well with that for *cis*-[Co (en)₂ (aniline) Cl]²⁺ ($k_2=6.27 \times 10^{-8}$ M sec⁻¹ at 50°C, I=0.07M)¹⁰. Presumably the conjugate base of *cis*- β -[Co (trien) (aniline) Cl]²⁺ is formed by the deprotonation of coordinated aniline and aquation in the k_2 path proceeds via this form to a large extent.

References

1. R. G. PEARSON, C. R. BOSTON and F. BASOLO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 304.
2. B. DAS SARMA and J. C. BAILAR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5480.
3. J. SELBIN and J. C. BAILAR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1524.
4. A. M. SARGESON and G. H. SEARLE, *Nature*, 1963, **200**, 356; A. M. SARGESON and G. H. SEARLE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 45.
5. A. M. SARGESON and G. H. SEARLE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 787; 1967, **6**, 1032.
6. D. A. BUCKINGHAM and L. G. MARZILLI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1042.
7. D. A. BUCKINGHAM, P. J. CRESSWELL, R. J. DELLACA, M. DWYER, G. J. GAINSFORD, L. G. MARZILLI, I. E. MAXWELL, W. T. ROBINSON, A. M. SARGESON and K. R. TURNBULL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 1713.
8. F. BASOLO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 2634.
9. N. C. NAIK and R. K. NANDA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 3793 and references cited therein.
10. R. N. NANDA and R. K. NANDA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 104.
11. Z. ZSAKO', Cs. VARHELYI and DOBOCAN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 1459.
12. F. BASOLO, J. G. BERGMANN, R. E. MEEKER and R. G. PEARSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 2676.
13. M. L. TOBE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1260.